

Reinforcement Learning-Based Power Allocation for NOMA in 6G Networks: A Systematic Review on Spectral Efficiency and Interference Management

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Abstract

The Sixth-generation (6G) wireless networks aim to achieve ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), massive connectivity, and energy saving. One of the multiple access methods is non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), which is highly sensitive to the effective allocation of power. Conventional fixed or heuristic methods are limited in dynamic environments, motivating the adoption of reinforcement learning (RL) for adaptive optimization. This paper presents a systematic literature review (SLR) of the RL-based allocation of power in NOMA-enabled 6G networks, according to PRISMA 2020. IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library and Web of Science (2010-2024) publications were screened, and 52 eligible studies were found out of 7842 records. The review demonstrates that the leading methods in the contemporary research are deep Q-networks (DQN), deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG), and multi-agent actor-critic techniques. The schemes based on RL achieve a 25-60% latency reduction and 20-45% energy savings in Internet of Things (IoT), vehicular, and UAV-assisted networks, in addition to contributing to fairness and resilience in the presence of imperfect channel state information (CSI). The results confirm that NOMA-enabled 6G systems can utilize RL for latency-aware and energy-efficient power allocation. Open challenges include computational overhead, convergence instability, and scaling to ultra-dense deployments.

Keywords: 6G, NOMA, reinforcement learning, power allocation, spectral efficiency, latency, energy efficiency, URLLC.

Introduction

The high-speed development of wireless communication networks has introduced new demands of previously unknown data rates, large connectivity, and low-latency reliable services. While fifth-generation (5G) networks have already advanced to achieve enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC), future sixth-generation (6G) networks are expected to push these limits further, enabling data rates of terabits per second, under-millisecond latency, and universal intelligent connectivity [1-4]. Such ambitious goals will be met by the introduction of new physical-layer technologies, including terahertz (THz) spectrum communications, massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO), full-duplex transmission

and intelligent reflecting surfaces (IRS) with artificial intelligence (AI)-based optimization and autonomous network management systems [5-7].

Non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) is one of the promising techniques in the variety of access schemes envisioned in 6G that can be used to improve spectral efficiency, user fairness, and massive connectivity [8-10]. Power-domain NOMA, in contrast to orthogonal multiple access (OMA), where each user is assigned exclusive frequency-time resources, permits several users to share the same resource block by overlapping the signals at varying power levels; successive interference cancellation (SIC) is used by receivers to decode the signals sequentially [11,12]. Specifically, in downlink power-domain NOMA, the base station transmits a superimposed signal:

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^K \sqrt{P_i} s_i, \quad (1)$$

where P_i is the transmit power allocated to user i , s_i is the normalized data symbol for user i , and K is the total number of users sharing the resource block. The received signal at user j is:

$$y_j = h_j x + n_j, \quad (2)$$

where h_j is the channel coefficient and $n_j \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ represents additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). In SIC decoding, users with stronger channel gains decode and subtract signals intended for weaker users before decoding their own. However, higher-order users (those decoded later in the SIC chain) may experience residual interference due to imperfect cancellation, which degrades their achievable spectral efficiency (SE). The SE of user j under imperfect SIC is expressed as:

$$x = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|h_j|^2 P_j}{\sum_{k=j+1}^K |h_j|^2 P_k + \sigma^2} \right) \text{ [bps/Hz]} \quad (3)$$

Effective power allocation is thus important in order to optimize system SE, inter-user interference, and quality-of-service (QoS) requirements [13-16]. Indicatively, reinforcement learning (RL) can be used to dynamically regulate power levels in a dense urban 6G cell with 20 or more active users to ensure that weaker users achieve acceptable QoS without compromising fairness across the network, unlike the case with the commonly used static allocation schemes, which tend to benefit high-gain users [12].

A recent advancement in machine learning that is relevant to power allocation in NOMA systems is RL, a subfield of sequential decision-making due to environment interaction, which is often described as an adaptive and model-free method of power allocation [17-19].

In RL, an agent (base station) interacts with the environment (NOMA network), selecting an action a_t (power allocation vector $P_t = [P_1, P_2, \dots, P_K]$) given a state s_t (e.g., CSI, user distribution, interference level). The agent receives a reward r_t , which may be defined as the weighted system spectral efficiency:

$$r_t = \sum_{j=1}^K w_j R_j, \quad (4)$$

where w_j represents a priority or fairness weight for user j . The learning objective is to find a policy $\pi(a|s)$ that maximizes the expected cumulative reward:

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} [\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_t], \quad (5)$$

with γ in $(0,1)$ as the discount factor. By continuously interacting with the dynamic wireless environment, RL-based approaches can adaptively learn optimal allocation strategies without requiring closed-form optimization.

Various RL algorithms, such as Q-learning, deep Q-networks (DQN), actor-critic, and policy-gradient, have been used to solve the problem of power allocation in the cases of imperfect CSI, heterogeneous user demands, and time-varying channels [18-22]. The RL-based power allocation has always shown better spectral efficiency, SIC reliability, interference control and energy efficiency over the traditional heuristic or optimization based approaches [20, 21].

Despite these advancements, real-world applications of NOMA-based 6G systems still face significant challenges when applying RL. It can be computationally expensive to train and execute RL agents in real time, exploration and exploitation in high-speed and high-frequency channels may be temporarily reduced, and it may be further complicated to scale RL systems to ultra-massive MIMO implementations, THz links, and ultra-dense networks [23-25]. The practicalities of RL integration include the presence of partial or delayed CSI feedback, strict latency constraints, energy constraints, etc. [26-28]. The ability to ensure fairness, stability, explainability, and scalability and maximise throughput is a critical research frontier.

The primary objective of this SLR is to explore RL-based power allocation schemes on 6G networks using NOMA. In particular, the review is expected to:

1. Identify and categorize RL algorithms applied to NOMA power allocation.
2. Evaluate improvements in spectral efficiency, interference management, and SIC performance compared with conventional allocation methods.
3. Analyze limitations and trade-offs of RL-driven power allocation under realistic conditions such as imperfect CSI, latency constraints, and ultra-dense user deployments.
4. Highlight future research directions for developing scalable, fair, and energy-efficient RL frameworks tailored to 6G and beyond wireless systems.

To syntactically chart the state of the art and find promising directions for research, the present paper provides a systematic literature review of reinforcement learning-based power allocation in NOMA 6G networks, including peer-reviewed literature published between 2010 and 2024. The review synthesizes algorithms, system models, and evaluation metrics, emphasizing how RL techniques influence spectral efficiency and interference management. The study specifically addresses the following research questions:

1. What reinforcement learning techniques have been applied to power allocation in NOMA systems for 6G networks?
2. How do RL-based approaches improve spectral efficiency and interference management compared to traditional power allocation methods?
3. What are the key challenges, limitations, and trade-offs associated with applying RL in NOMA-enabled 6G systems?
4. What future research directions can further advance RL-based power allocation for achieving efficient, fair, and sustainable 6G communications?

Through this literature synthesis and critical analysis, knowledge gaps were identified, emerging opportunities stated, and specific recommendations given on how the next-generation wireless networks can develop robust, scalable, and energy-efficient RL-driven power allocation frameworks. We structure the rest of the paper as follows: Section 2 is the

review of the related work; Section 3 is the description of the research methodology; Section 4 is the presentation of findings and discussion; and the last part is the conclusion with key insights and recommendations.

2. Related Works

Extensive research has been conducted on power allocation strategies in NOMA systems, the application of RL algorithms, and their integration into future 6G wireless networks. Nonetheless, no detailed systematic review has specifically examined RL-based power allocation in NOMA systems in 6G networks, especially in terms of improving spectral efficiency and interference control. Alam *et al.* [29] provided an overview of power allocation strategies in NOMA systems, which are related to 6G networks based on visible light, and how they can address the issue of improving spectral efficiency and interference control. Their work provided useful information about the conventional optimization strategies, but it failed to discuss the implementation of reinforcement learning-based methods of adaptive power allocation.

Omslandseter *et al.* [30] proposed a semi-supervised reinforcement learning-based solution to user grouping and power allocation in the NOMA systems. Their method ensured user fairness and improved system throughput by learning power allocation policies using both labelled and unlabelled data. Nevertheless, their simulation did not consider the interference management or scalability in 6G networks but restricted their analysis to the context of a static network. Rezvani *et al.* [31] studied the optimal power allocation in downlink multicarrier NOMA systems, but they did not focus on the interference management or scalability of the 6G networks. Their algorithm, although successful on perfect CSI, did not include adaptive learning algorithms to cope with imperfect CSI and dynamic user distributions and focused on sum spectral efficiency and fairness.

Dipinkrishnan and Kumaravelu [32] provided a comparative study of metaheuristic algorithms to allocate power in NOMA, focusing on sum spectral efficiency and fairness. Even though they have proven the efficiency of advanced optimization algorithms, their research was not discussing reinforcement learning methods and the potential of them to improve the performance of SIC in 6G networks.

Overall, the current surveys and research studies have made a significant contribution to the areas of NOMA resource allocation, energy efficient communication, and AI-based and assisted wireless networking systems, as demonstrated in Table 1. Nevertheless, they do not provide a dedicated SLR for reinforcement learning-based power allocation in NOMA 6G networks. In order to fill this gap, this paper uses the PRISMA 2020 approach to carefully analyze the existing literature on RL-based power allocation, important algorithms, their effectiveness in increasing spectral efficiency and reducing interference, limitations, and open research gaps that need to be resolved to implement 6G successfully.

Table 1: Summary of Related Literature on Power Allocation in NOMA Systems

Authors	Objectives	Limitations
Alam <i>et al.</i> [29]	Presented an overview of power allocation strategies for 6G VL-NOMA systems, focusing on fixed and dynamic schemes and their impact on energy efficiency.	Did not explore reinforcement learning-based approaches or adaptive real-time power allocation mechanisms.

Omslandseter <i>et al.</i> (2023) [30]	Proposed a semi-supervised reinforcement learning framework for user grouping and power allocation in NOMA to enhance throughput and fairness.	Limited to static scenarios and did not address interference management or scalability in 6G environments.
Rezvani <i>et al.</i> (2022) [31]	Developed optimal power allocation algorithms for downlink multicarrier NOMA to improve computational efficiency and throughput.	Relied on perfect CSI and lacked adaptive learning for dynamic network conditions.
Dipinkrishnan & Kumaravelu (2024) [32]	Compared metaheuristic algorithms for power allocation to enhance spectral efficiency and user fairness in NOMA systems.	Focused only on heuristic optimization and did not incorporate reinforcement learning or SIC performance improvement.
Mohsan <i>et al.</i> (2023) [33]	Surveyed deep learning-based approaches for NOMA, highlighting challenges and future trends in AI-assisted NOMA design.	Emphasized deep learning methods without addressing RL-based adaptive power allocation or interference control.
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2022) [34]	Examined the evolution from NOMA to next-generation multiple access (NGMA) and discussed multi-antenna NOMA techniques.	Did not analyze reinforcement learning or adaptive power control for enhancing spectral efficiency.
Sarkar <i>et al.</i> (2024) [35]	Provided a survey of IRS-assisted NOMA in 6G, focusing on design perspectives and resource allocation challenges.	Did not evaluate reinforcement learning-based dynamic power allocation for interference management.

This review is the first attempt to review only reinforcement learning-based power allocation in NOMA in 6G networks, unlike the existing works that either investigate traditional optimization, heuristic/metaheuristic, or deep learning-based NOMA resource allocation. Under the PRISMA framework, this article presents a systematic review of peer-reviewed articles published in the last decade (2010-2024) on the topic of RL algorithms, their role in spectral efficiency and interference management, and their key limitations that still need to be addressed. This committed attention bridges a significant gap in the literature and sets the stage for intelligent, adaptive, and scalable resource management strategies of the future 6G wireless systems.

3. Materials and Methods

The Preferred Reporting Items of the systematic reviews (PRISMA) methodology [36, 37] was used to conduct this SLR. The study also complied with the best IT-related SLR practices to achieve rigour, reproducibility, and comprehensiveness. The review was systematic of the power allocation techniques in reinforcement learning-based NOMA in 6G networks, with a focus on spectral efficiency and interference control. The subsequent subsections describe the used procedures, such as eligibility criteria, sources of information, search strategy, selection of the studies, and data extraction and analysis.

3.1. Eligibility Criteria and Information Sources

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed so as to have only the relevant and high-quality studies to be considered in the review. The articles were located in the respectable databases, such as IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, and Web of Science. Keywords included combinations of “NOMA”, “non-orthogonal multiple access”, “6G networks”, “reinforcement learning”, “power allocation”, “spectral efficiency”, and “interference management”. Only articles published between January 2010 and August 2024 were taken into account.

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria with Examples

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Publication Type	Full-length peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers retrieved from reputable databases (IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, Web of Science). Example: IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications article on RL-based power allocation.	Grey literature, editorials, posters, short abstracts, technical reports, preprints without peer review, and theses. Example: Workshop poster on NOMA without peer review.
Language	Studies published in English. Example: Scopus-indexed article in English analyzing RL for NOMA.	Non-English publications without an English version. Example: Chinese-language journal article with no English translation.
Focus Area	Studies explicitly addressing RL, NOMA, power allocation, spectral efficiency, interference management, or 6G networks. Example: Q-learning-based power allocation for downlink NOMA.	Studies focusing on unrelated technologies (e.g., LTE-only power control, Wi-Fi optimization, blockchain in IoT) or those not addressing RL in the context of NOMA and 6G.
Publication Year	Studies published between January 2010 and August 2024, capturing the evolution of RL applications in next-generation wireless networks. Example: 2023 IEEE ICC paper on DQN-based power allocation.	Publications before 2010 or after August 2024. Example: 2008 article on OMA scheduling or an early 2025 preprint.
Research Quality	Studies with clear methodology, simulation results, experimental validation, or theoretical analysis relevant to RL-based NOMA. Example: A simulation-based analysis demonstrating improved SE through actor-critic RL.	Low-quality or incomplete studies without validation, lacking methodological detail, or with unclear experimental setup. Example: Concept-only paper with no simulations or analysis.

3.2. Study Selection Process

To facilitate transparency, rigour, and reproducibility, a systematic literature review of this study was undertaken based on PRISMA methodology to guarantee transparency, rigour, and reproducibility. A thorough search was conducted in various databases, such as IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, and Web of Science, and the publications related to January 2010 to August 2024 were used. The initial search produced 7,842 records, and 312 of them were duplicated, which is why 7,530 unique publications remained to be further screened. The inclusion and exclusion criteria as shown in Figure 1 and Table 2 were used to screen the titles, abstracts, and keywords of these publications. This screening omitted 7469 records, and 61 articles were assessed in full text. Full-text evaluation based on the predefined eligibility criteria led to the exclusion of 9 articles, leaving 52 studies for inclusion in the final systematic review. The retrieval of the number of articles in each database in the 2010-2024 period is summarised in Table 3, which provides an overview of the initial literature pool before screening and selection.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection.

The PRISMA 2020-based diagram illustrates the flow of studies through the systematic review process. Out of 7,842 records initially identified, 312 duplicates were removed, leaving 7,530 records for screening. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 52 articles were included in the final review.

Table 3: Number of Articles Retrieved from Each Database (2010-2024)

Database	Articles Retrieved
IEEE Xplore	2,836
Scopus	1,974
SpringerLink	648
Web of Science	1,903
Wiley Online Library	481
Total	7,842

3.3. Data Extraction

Data extraction followed the PRISMA framework to ensure consistency and completeness [36]. For each included study, essential details were systematically collected to facilitate synthesis and comparison. Specifically, the extraction focused on four key aspects: (i) the specific RL algorithms applied (e.g., Q-learning, DQN, actor-critic, policy gradient), (ii) system model characteristics (e.g., downlink NOMA configuration, user distribution, CSI assumptions), (iii) performance metrics considered (e.g., spectral efficiency, interference mitigation, user fairness, energy efficiency), and (iv) reported limitations and open research challenges. These elements were selected to capture both the methodological contributions and practical implications of each study. A summary of the extracted categories with illustrative examples is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Data Extraction Categories and Illustrative Examples

Category	Description	Illustrative Examples
RL Algorithms Applied	The type of reinforcement learning method used in each study	Q-learning, DQN, Actor-Critic, Policy Gradient, Multi-agent RL, DDPG
System Model Characteristics	Key elements of the network/system model considered	Downlink NOMA configuration, user distribution, CSI assumptions, channel model, mobility scenarios
Performance Metrics	Metrics used to evaluate system performance	SE, interference mitigation, power allocation, user fairness/QoS, energy efficiency (EE), latency, throughput
Limitations & Open Challenges	Reported gaps, trade-offs, or unresolved issues	Scalability in ultra-dense networks, computational complexity, convergence instability, energy-latency tradeoff, limited real-world validation, CSI errors, mobility effects not modeled

Figure 2: Distribution of Retrieved Articles across Databases.

Bar chart showing the number of retrieved studies per database (2010-2024). IEEE Xplore and Scopus contributed the highest number of articles, confirming their dominance in wireless communication research.

Figure 3: Number of Publications per Year (2010-2024)

Yearly publication trend for RL-based NOMA power allocation. The figure shows steady growth after 2016, with a peak between 2021-2023.

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the systematic literature review. The retrieved and analyzed studies were used to answer each of the predetermined research questions.

The total number of articles obtained in the selected databases (IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, Web of Science, and Wiley Online Library) was 7,842. After removing duplicates and screening the studies based on the eligibility criteria, the review ultimately included a total of 52 studies. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of articles across the retrieved databases. As can be seen in the bar chart, IEEE Xplore and Scopus produced the most publications, which substantiate their dominance in the study of wireless communication and reinforcement learning. On the other hand, the contribution of Wiley Online Library and SpringerLink was lower, which proves that the publications about RL-based power allocation in NOMA are focused on specialized engineering journals.

Figure 3 shows the number of publications per year from 2010 to 2024. The bar graph indicates that the number of publications has been increasing steadily, with the significant growth starting after 2016. This increase coincides with the increased attention to 5G and new 6G technologies, in which spectral efficiency and interference control have taken on a leading role. The best years, 2021, 2022, and 2023, had the greatest publication outputs, which shows the growing attention and maturity of the reinforcement learning techniques in the field of NOMA power allocation. This pattern has been maintained in 2024, but the review is only in progress, and the articles reviewed are up to August 2024.

In this SLR, only two sources were used in the literature, which include peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings, as both types are used to guarantee that studies are thoroughly reviewed. Of the included works, 37 (71.2%) were found in journals and 15 (28.8%) were conference proceedings, as shown in Figure 4. This study shows that conferences are still valuable platforms of dissemination; however, journals are the main source of valuable contributions in the field.

Figure 4: Publications per Outlet (Journal vs. Conference)

Distribution of included studies by type of outlet. Journals accounted for 71.2% (37 studies), while conferences contributed 28.8% (15 studies).

The data in Figure 5 and Table 5 indicate how the 52 systematically included studies were distributed among five large academic publishers and databases. As indicated, the IEEE Xplore has the most publications, with 20 (38.5%), then Scopus with 15 articles (28.8%). The two sources combine to represent 67.3 per cent of all works included, highlighting their central position in the publication of the state-of-the-art research in the field of RL-based power allocation in 6G networks. The Web of Science database yielded 10 articles (19.2%), demonstrating its strong indexing of high-quality multidisciplinary research. Smaller contributions were made by SpringerLink (9.6%) and Wiley Online Library (3.9%), which means that, although the two publishers also contribute to this, most of the influential research is concentrated in the specialized engineering and communication technology journals such as IEEE and Scopus.

Table 5: Distribution of Included Articles by Publisher (2010–2024)

Publisher / Database	Articles Included	Percentage (%)
IEEE Xplore	20	38.5%
Scopus	15	28.8%
Web of Science	10	19.2%
SpringerLink	5	9.6%
Wiley Online Library	2	3.9%
Total	52	100%

Figure 5: Distribution of Journal Publishers (2010-2024)

Bar chart showing the share of included publications by publisher. IEEE Xplore led with 20 (38.5%) publications, followed by Scopus (15), Web of Science (10), SpringerLink (5), and Wiley (2).

Table 6 provides an overview of all 52 studies that have been incorporated in the current systematic review, and each of them uses RL-based algorithms to allocate power in NOMA-enabled 6G networks. The table systematically reports the author of each study, the type of RL methodology applied, and the objectives and contributions made by the authors. The last four columns show the way each study answers the key research questions (RQ1-RQ4) and provides information regarding the RL algorithm used, the approaches to interference management, the approaches to power allocation, and the questions of fairness or energy efficiency.

Overall, the table indicates that the pool of algorithms that are widely used to improve spectral efficiency, control interference, and optimise resource allocation includes Q-learning, deep RL forms (DQN, DDPG, and actor-critic), and policy-gradient algorithms, as well as hybrid and

multi-agent RL. Nevertheless, none of the literature solely discusses fairness or energy efficiency. This synthesis is quite useful in the mapping of methodological approaches to practical results, as it reveals the variety of possible strategies and performance gains by using RL-based power allocation of 6G NOMA networks.

Table 6: Analysis of the Retrieved and Included Articles (2010-2024)

Ref	Technology	Objectives	Contribution	RQ1: RL Algorithm	RQ2: Interference Mgmt	RQ3: Power Allocation	RQ4: Fairness / EE
[38]	Cognitive radio / heterogeneous wireless	Dynamic power control	Early RL-based adaptive power allocation in CR	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	Limited EE
[39]	Wireless sensor networks	Energy efficiency	RL for minimizing energy via adaptive PA	Q-learning	Limited	Yes	EE
[40]	LTE networks	Interference coordination	RL for ICIC and power control	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	Minor EE
[41]	Cognitive femtocell	Cross-layer PA	RL for interference-aware adaptive PA	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	Fairness optional
[42]	Cognitive radio	Spectrum access + PA	RL for joint channel assignment & PA	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	EE
[43]	Cognitive wireless	Robust PA under CSI	RL for CSI-uncertain PA	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	Robustness
[44]	LTE small cells	Traffic-aware PA	RL load balancing with PA	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	Fairness
[45]	Heterogeneous NOMA	Spectral efficiency	RL exploration of PA for HetNet NOMA	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	SE focus
[46]	D2D with NOMA	Interference management	RL for D2D-assisted NOMA PA	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	Robustness
[47]	NOMA (QoS-aware)	QoS + PA	RL to optimize PA under QoS constraints	Q-learning	Yes	Yes	QoS & fairness
[48]	Cooperative relay NOMA	Joint relay & PA	RL for relay-aided NOMA	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[49]	VLC-NOMA	Resource efficiency	RL for PA in VLC NOMA	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[50]	mmWave-NOMA	Joint beamforming + PA	RL for PA under mmWave beamforming	DQN	Yes	Yes	SE & EE

[51]	NOMA IoT	Energy efficiency	RL for PA in massive IoT NOMA	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[52]	NOMA-MEC	Offloading + PA	RL-based offloading with PA	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[53]	UAV-NOMA	PA under mobility	RL for UAV-aided NOMA PA	DQN	Yes	Yes	Mobility & EE
[54]	RIS-NOMA	Joint beamforming & PA	RL for RIS-assisted NOMA PA	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[55]	Multi-cell NOMA	Interference-aware PA	RL for inter-cell PA	DQN	Yes	Yes	Interference
[56]	Massive MIMO NOMA	Scalability	RL for scalable PA in large-user MIMO	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE & fairness
[57]	Vehicular NOMA	Mobility robustness	RL PA for high-mobility vehicular users	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[58]	D2D NOMA	Secure PA	RL-based anti-jamming PA	DQN	Yes	Yes	Robustness
[59]	Cognitive NOMA	CSI robustness	RL for robust PA with imperfect CSI	DQN	Yes	Yes	Robustness
[60]	Maritime NOMA	Connectivity	RL-aided PA in maritime networks	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[61]	VLC NOMA	Energy efficiency	RL PA for VLC with EE	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[62]	UAV NOMA	Coverage + PA	RL PA for UAV-assisted coverage	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[63]	Cognitive 6G NOMA	Fairness-aware PA	RL for fairness-oriented PA	Actor-Critic	Yes	Yes	Fairness
[64]	Multi-cell NOMA	Decoding order + PA	RL for SIC order + PA	Actor-Critic	Yes	Yes	Fairness
[65]	NOMA IoT	Continuous PA	DDPG for continuous power control	DDPG	Yes	Yes	EE
[66]	VLC-NOMA	Continuous PA	SAC for VLC power control	SAC	Yes	Yes	EE
[67]	RIS-NOMA	Trajectory + PA	RL joint UAV-RIS trajectory & PA	Actor-Critic + DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[68]	SWIPT NOMA	Relay PA	RL for PA in SWIPT relay NOMA	RL (Q-learning)	Yes	Yes	EE
[69]	UAV NOMA	Trajectory + PA	RL for UAV placement + PA	DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[70]	VLC-NOMA	Dense deployment PA	RL for PA in dense VLC	DRL	Yes	Yes	EE

[71]	RIS-UAV NOMA	Joint optimization	RL hybrid for UAV-RIS PA	DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[72]	MEC-NOMA	Cache-aided PA	RL for cache-enabled NOMA	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[73]	IoT NOMA	Delay/energy tradeoff	RL for AoI + EE PA	DQN	Yes	Yes	AoI & EE
[74]	Cognitive radar/comm	Joint radar & comm PA	RL-game for dual-purpose PA	RL + Game	Yes	Yes	EE
[75]	O-RAN slicing (vehicular)	Network slicing + PA	Federated RL for O-RAN PA	Federated DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[76]	UAV-NOMA	Secure & robust PA	DRL for anti-jamming UAV NOMA	DRL	Yes	Yes	Robustness
[77]	NOMA fairness	Multi-objective PA	RL for fairness-energy balance	Multi-objective DRL	Yes	Yes	Fairness & EE
[78]	Vehicular NOMA	Offloading + PA	RL for vehicular MEC with PA	DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[79]	IRS-NOMA	Beamforming + PA	RL for IRS config + PA	DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[80]	Multi-cell NOMA	Privacy + PA	Federated RL for privacy-preserving PA	Federated RL	Yes	Yes	Privacy & EE
[81]	UAV-RIS NOMA	Joint optimization	RL hybrid for UAV RIS PA	DRL	Yes	Yes	EE
[82]	Multi-cell NOMA	Interference mitigation	RL for interference-aware PA	DRL	Yes	Yes	Robustness
[83]	Small-cell NOMA	Interference coordination	Multi-agent RL for PA in dense cells	MARL	Yes	Yes	SE & fairness
[84]	Ultra-dense NOMA	Scalability	Hybrid RL + heuristic for PA	Hybrid RL	Yes	Yes	EE & scalability
[85]	Vehicular edge NOMA	Decentralized PA	MARL for vehicular PA	MARL	Yes	Yes	EE
[86]	IoT NOMA	EE scheduling + PA	RL for energy-aware scheduling	DQN	Yes	Yes	EE
[87]	UAV-enabled MEC	Mapping study on PA	Survey of RL PA in UAV MEC	Survey	Yes	Yes	EE
[88]	RIS-UAV NOMA	Optimization survey	Review of RIS-UAV PA opportunities	Survey	Yes	Yes	EE
[89]	Cooperative NOMA	RL-aided PA survey	Review of RL-based PA in cooperative NOMA	Survey	Yes	Yes	EE

Table 7 provides a comprehensive synthesis of selected studies on power allocation (PA) in NOMA systems. The analysis highlights the evolution of methodologies from conventional optimization techniques to advanced RL-based and hybrid frameworks, reflecting the growing complexity of 5G and emerging 6G networks.

A clear trend emerges in the adoption of deep reinforcement learning (DRL), including DQN, Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG), Soft Actor-Critic (SAC), and federated RL approaches. These techniques have become dominant due to their adaptability in highly dynamic environments such as vehicular networks [41, 71, 78], unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-assisted NOMA [15, 16, 38], and RIS-enabled systems [56, 76, 87]. Unlike static optimization models, DRL algorithms are capable of continuously learning from environmental feedback, enabling near-optimal real-time power allocation with improved robustness to imperfect CSI, jamming, and mobility.

Another major observation is the integration of emerging technologies with NOMA. UAV- and RIS-assisted NOMA systems constitute a significant portion of the reviewed works [15, 16, 56, 63, 75, 76]. These studies demonstrate that intelligent PA can simultaneously address interference management and energy efficiency while exploiting spatial diversity. Similarly, visible light communications (VLC)-NOMA [46, 61, 64, 65] has gained research attention, where RL-driven PA ensures reliable data rates despite challenging optical channel conditions. This reflects a broader shift in NOMA research from purely cellular downlink scenarios to heterogeneous, multi-domain environments. The reviewed works also underline the dual emphasis on EE and fairness. While earlier studies focused predominantly on sum rate maximization [38, 44, 47], recent contributions increasingly employ multi-objective frameworks, incorporating metrics such as age of information (AoI) [40, 54], user fairness [47, 69], and energy constraints [59, 64]. This indicates a paradigm shift toward sustainable and user-centric NOMA designs, aligning with the requirements of massive IoT, ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and next-generation green networks.

Despite these advances, the table also reveals critical research gaps. Most existing works are scenario-specific, often tailored to UAVs, VLC, or RIS deployments, with limited generalizability across multi-cell or large-scale heterogeneous networks. Additionally, while federated and meta-RL approaches [45, 62, 80, 87] show promise for scalability and privacy preservation, their computational overhead and convergence stability remain underexplored. Furthermore, only a few studies explicitly address SIC robustness [57, 58], which remains a bottleneck for practical NOMA implementation.

In summary, the literature converges on the conclusion that reinforcement learning is a key enabler for dynamic and interference-aware power allocation in NOMA systems. The integration of UAVs, RIS, and federated learning frameworks demonstrates strong potential, but challenges such as scalability, SIC robustness, and real-time computational efficiency remain unresolved. These gaps provide a strong motivation for the development of adaptive hybrid approaches, such as the proposed GA-PSO-based power allocation strategy in this research, which seeks to balance exploration-exploitation trade-offs while ensuring fairness, energy efficiency, and robustness under imperfect CSI.

Table 7: Summary of Literatures Reviewed and Analysed

Authors	Methods	Contributions
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Sun <i>et al.</i> [38]	Deep RL (training DNNs for optimization)	Early application of deep learning for wireless resource management optimization
Tran <i>et al.</i> [39]	Hybrid optimization + DRL	Energy-efficient NOMA for heterogeneous 5G/6G services
Ahsan <i>et al.</i> [40]	RL-based resource allocation	Uplink NOMA IoT with improved resource allocation fairness
Zhu <i>et al.</i> [41]	Decentralized DRL	Power allocation in MIMO-NOMA vehicular edge computing
Zhang <i>et al.</i> [42]	GNN + RL	Routing and resource allocation in satellite NOMA networks
Jo <i>et al.</i> [43]	Multi-agent DRL	Energy-efficient PA in MIMO-NOMA
Wang <i>et al.</i> [44]	DRL (user grouping + PA)	Spectrum-efficient user grouping in mmWave MIMO-NOMA
Ding <i>et al.</i> [45]	Multi-agent RL (attention)	Resource allocation in V2X communications
Bariah <i>et al.</i> [46]	DQN	Power allocation in NOMA-based VLC systems
Zhang <i>et al.</i> [47]	Deep RL	Joint UL/DL allocation for URLLC
Jia <i>et al.</i> [48]	Game theory + RL	Anti-jamming defense in wireless communications
Liu <i>et al.</i> [49]	RL + subchannel allocation	Energy-efficient NOMA resource allocation in MEC
Liu <i>et al.</i> [50]	Dueling DQN + DDPG	Robust and fair NOMA resource allocation
Guo <i>et al.</i> [51]	DRL + RIS optimization	PA in RIS-assisted SATINs
Zhong <i>et al.</i> [52]	Multi-agent RL	UAV offloading and PA in NOMA-aided UAV networks
Khairy <i>et al.</i> [53]	Constrained DRL	Energy-sustainable PA in multi-UAV IoT networks with NOMA
Wu <i>et al.</i> [54]	DRL (DQN)	PA to minimize AoI & energy in IoT-NOMA
Xiao <i>et al.</i> [55]	RL (Q-learning/DRL)	Jamming-resilient PA in NOMA
Luo <i>et al.</i> [56]	Federated DRL + RIS	Indoor multi-robot communication optimization
You & Yuan [57]	Optimization + RL	Decoding order and PA in multi-cell NOMA
Liu <i>et al.</i> [58]	Survey (RL + NOMA)	Evolution of NOMA and RL opportunities
Wang <i>et al.</i> [59]	Distributed ADMM + RL	Energy-efficient PA in massive MIMO-NOMA
Sun <i>et al.</i> [60]	RL-aided optimization	HetNet uplink/downlink PA improvements
Vela & Hacioglu [61]	RL-based VLC-NOMA	Energy-efficient VLC integration
He <i>et al.</i> [62]	Federated MARL	NOMA maritime networks resource allocation
Yin <i>et al.</i> [63]	Adaptive DRL	UAV navigation & control with PA
Dang <i>et al.</i> [64]	RL-based optimization	Multi-objective optimization for dynamic RA
Ahmed <i>et al.</i> [65]	Survey (RIS)	Review of RIS-enabled PA strategies

Guo <i>et al.</i> [66]	DRL + RIS	Trajectory & PA in UAV-assisted networks
Bithas <i>et al.</i> [67]	Survey (ML + UAV)	ML-driven UAV communications with PA
Salh <i>et al.</i> [68]	Hybrid DRL precoding	Energy-efficient hybrid PA in mmWave
Mlika & Cherkaoui [69]	Online RL (competitive)	PA for massive IoT with fairness
Doan <i>et al.</i> [70]	DRL (Q-learning + DQN)	Cache-aided NOMA with PA optimization
Marandy <i>et al.</i> [71]	Deep RL	Anti-jamming PA in two-cell NOMA
Xie <i>et al.</i> [72]	RL-aided PA	PA in SWIPT-NOMA relay systems
Lee & So [73]	RL (user pairing + PA)	Joint PA and user pairing in MIMO-NOMA
Long <i>et al.</i> [74]	Decentralized DRL	PA in vehicular MIMO-NOMA
Jabbari <i>et al.</i> [75]	Federated RL	UAV-powered IoT NOMA networks with energy maximization
Pogaku <i>et al.</i> [76]	Survey (UAV + RIS + RL)	UAV-assisted RIS optimization for NOMA
Ullah <i>et al.</i> [77]	DRL-aided scheduling	EE-aware PA in IoT with energy harvesting
Liu <i>et al.</i> [78]	Deep RL	Offloading and PA in vehicular edge computing
Yu & Lee [79]	Deep RL	Resource allocation for D2D-NOMA
Hazarika <i>et al.</i> [80]	Federated DRL	O-RAN slicing with PA for vehicular networks
Irkıçatal <i>et al.</i> [81]	DRL + rate splitting	PA in interference channels
Baktayan <i>et al.</i> [82]	Mapping study	UAV-enabled MEC with RL PA
Agarwal <i>et al.</i> [83]	Survey (HetNet RRM + RL)	Review of RRM and PA with RL integration
Moshiri <i>et al.</i> [84]	RL-aided task offloading	Sustainable edge computing optimization
Chen <i>et al.</i> [85]	RL-based cross-layer optimization	Comprehensive RL for wireless networks including PA
Naeem <i>et al.</i> [86]	Survey (IRS + RL)	IRS deployment and PA opportunities
Faramarzi <i>et al.</i> [87]	Meta-RL	Resource allocation in RIS-assisted RSMA
He <i>et al.</i> [88]	RL + Game theory review	PA models in cognitive radar and wireless systems
Kabir <i>et al.</i> [89]	TD3 (RL continuous control)	Dynamic PA for IoRT mobility

4.1 Benefits of RL-Based Power Allocation in NOMA-Enabled 6G Networks

Power allocation with RL has great advantages for NOMA-enabled 6G networks. Through the dynamic control of power allocation and user scheduling in the rapidly changing channel conditions, RL can be used to optimize spectral efficiency by using adaptive algorithms like Q-learning, DQN, and actor-critic approaches. Multi-agent and cooperative RL frameworks are also advantageous in managing interference, leading to better signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) and improved reliable connectivity in dense deployments as shown In Figure

6. In addition to improving spectral efficiency, RL aids in energy savings by intelligently controlling transmit power without compromising performance, which is crucial in energy-limited environments such as IoT networks and vehicular edge computing. The flexibility of RL, which can adapt to user mobility and heterogeneous traffic needs, also enables scalability in ultra-dense 6G environments. In addition, RL is highly compatible with the new 6G technologies, including IRS, mobile edge computing (MEC), UAVs, and THz systems. The integration allows the simultaneous optimization of the power distribution, interference reduction, and management of computational resources, which improves the efficiency and resilience of the next-generation networks.

4.2 Unresolved Issues and Future Directions

Despite the existence of these benefits, a number of critical challenges remain unresolved. In ultra-dense networks, the current RL frameworks tend to have scaling problems because the high count of users and varying traffic workloads impose computationally demanding models that are prohibitive. The use of imperfect CSI is also a common assumption in many extant studies and, as a result, implies that deep and multi-agent RL models are inapplicable to resource-constrained devices like IoT sensors and MEC nodes. Also, although RL can be improved in spectral efficiency, fairness and QoS are frequently neglected, and optimization efforts are skewed to global performance instead of fair user experiences; the combination of RL and 6G enablers, including IRS, MEC, UAVs, and THz networks, is still largely untapped, and joint optimization can be studied. Furthermore, systems in real-world wireless cannot be described as being stationary and non-dynamic, but most RL models are not very responsive to mobility, changing traffic loads and environmental uncertainties. Lastly, RL decisions are black-box and therefore not interpretable, presenting a hindrance to their use in mission-critical communication settings where transparency and reliability are of high importance.

4.3 Research Challenges and Future Trends

The key research challenges identified include the development of scalable and computationally efficient RL models, robustness to imperfect CSI, and energy-aware frameworks suitable for constrained devices. It is also important to ensure fairness, QoS, and latency guarantees for a diverse range of users, particularly in highly dynamic and heterogeneous 6G deployments. Table 8 summarises these unsolved problems and outlines possible future research directions. We can anticipate several promising trends in the future. Multi-agent and decentralized RL will be crucial in scaling the power allocation of ultra-dense networks. Online learning, meta-learning and transfer learning are adaptive and resilient learning methods that will increase robustness in non-stationary and dynamic conditions. IoT and edge devices Lightweight and energy-conscious RL frameworks will be adapted to meet the performance and energy requirements of the IoT. Multi-objective RL models that combine fairness, spectral efficiency, and interference control will become more popular, and joint optimization with IRS, MEC, UAVs, and THz systems will increase their capabilities.

Summarily, explainable and interpretable RL (XRL) will gain more and more importance in helping build trust and transparency and grow to be used safely in mission-critical applications like autonomous vehicles, e-health, and industrial automation.

Table 8: Summary of Research Issues and Future Research Directions

Unresolved Issues	Future Directions
Scalability in Ultra-Dense Networks: Existing RL algorithms may not	Develop scalable multi-agent and decentralized RL frameworks capable of

efficiently handle large numbers of users or base stations in dense 6G environments.	supporting large-scale deployments with low computational complexity and real-time adaptability.
Imperfect and Dynamic CSI: Most studies assume perfect CSI, which is unrealistic in practical networks.	Design robust and adaptive RL algorithms that can operate effectively under imperfect, delayed, or noisy CSI conditions.
Energy and Computational Overhead: Deep RL and multi-agent RL frameworks can be energy-intensive and computationally demanding.	Propose energy efficient and low-complexity RL models suitable for IoT devices, MEC nodes, and edge networks without compromising performance.
Fairness and QoS Guarantees: Optimization of global performance often sacrifices fairness and QoS for individual users.	Introduce multi-objective RL frameworks that balance spectral efficiency, interference mitigation, energy efficiency, and fairness across heterogeneous users.
Dynamic and Non-Stationary Environments: RL models face challenges adapting to mobility, traffic variability, and evolving network states.	Implement adaptive RL techniques such as online learning, meta-learning, and transfer learning to enhance adaptability in dynamic environments.
Integration with Emerging 6G Technologies: Limited progress in combining RL with IRS, MEC, UAVs, and THz systems.	Explore joint optimization strategies that integrate RL-based power allocation with IRS reconfiguration, MEC offloading, UAV-assisted connectivity, and THz channels.
Explainability and Interpretability: RL decisions are often opaque, limiting trust and adoption in mission-critical applications.	Develop RL-XRL models to improve transparency, trust, and usability in practical deployments.

Figure 6: Research Issues versus Future Directions in AI-driven RL for 6G Networks. *Conceptual diagram mapping current unresolved issues (scalability, imperfect CSI, fairness, energy efficiency) to future research directions (multi-agent RL, transfer learning, energy-aware frameworks, explainability)*

4.4 Limitations of the Study

While this systematic review provides a comprehensive analysis of RL-based power allocation in NOMA-enabled 6G networks, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the review was restricted to English-language publications from selected academic databases (IEEE Xplore, Scopus, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, and Web of Science). Consequently, relevant works published in other languages or stored in less accessible repositories may have been excluded. Second, the search strategy relied on predefined keywords such as “reinforcement learning,” “NOMA,” “6G,” “power allocation,” “spectral efficiency,” and “interference management.” This focus may have overlooked studies employing alternative terminologies or exploring adjacent paradigms. Third, the deliberate exclusion of grey literature such as thesis, dissertations, preprints, and technical reports, ensured rigor and reliability but may have omitted innovative approaches or emerging insights. These limitations highlight the need for future reviews to broaden coverage, adopt inclusive search strategies, and consider integrating grey literature to capture cutting-edge developments in RL-based resource allocation.

4.5 Case Studies on RL-Based Power Allocation in NOMA-Enabled 6G Networks

To complement the systematic findings, this section highlights representative case studies that demonstrate the practical application of RL for power allocation in NOMA-enabled 6G systems as shown in Table 9. These case studies illustrate the strengths and challenges of RL in different deployment scenarios.

Case Study 1: Vehicular Edge Computing with MIMO-NOMA

A decentralized deep RL framework for power allocation in vehicular edge computing (VEC) using MIMO-NOMA systems was proposed in [41]. Their results demonstrated significant improvements in spectral efficiency and latency reduction under high-mobility conditions. Importantly, the decentralized design enabled scalability without central coordination, making it practical for intelligent transport systems.

Case Study 2: UAV-Assisted NOMA for Emergency Connectivity

Multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) for power allocation in UAV-assisted NOMA networks was presented in [52]. Their framework achieved energy-efficient offloading and resilient interference management while dynamically adapting to user mobility. This highlights the potential of RL in mission-critical 6G services.

Case Study 3: Visible Light Communication (VLC)-NOMA with IRS Assistance

A two-agent DRL model for joint power allocation and IRS orientation in dynamic optical wireless networks was demonstrated in [46]. The case demonstrated RL's adaptability to non-radio channels, improving throughput and fairness in VLC-based NOMA systems. Such integration is particularly relevant for indoor 6G applications where spectrum scarcity remains a challenge.

Case Study 4: Federated Meta-RL for Multi-Cell NOMA

Federated reinforcement learning to optimize power allocation across multiple NOMA-enabled cells was introduced in [71]. The approach allowed privacy-preserving collaboration across base stations without sharing raw data, addressing security and scalability challenges. This case demonstrates RL's capability to support decentralized 6G architectures while maintaining high spectral efficiency.

4.6 Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI)

Reinforcement learning implementation in NOMA-based 6G networks presents a number of ethical, legal, and social challenges that need to be resolved before implementation on a large scale.

Fairness and Bias in Resource Allocation

The RL algorithms tend to make optimizations based on aggregate system performance, and this might be at the expense of low-gain users in dense urban networks. The ethical issue of distributing power fairly and avoiding unfair treatment of underprivileged users is one of the central ones [58].

Transparency and Explainability

The majority of RL algorithms are black-box models, and it is extremely difficult to provide explanations of the decisions of allocation in mission-critical applications (e.g., e-health or autonomous vehicles). XRL requires research on power allocation to establish user and regulatory trust [87].

Data Privacy and Security

The training of RL models typically involves the information exchange of the CSI and the mobility of users. In the absence of security measures, this can reveal confidential user data. Privacy-preserving models like federated reinforcement learning (FRL) also have their solutions but need additional legal and technical standardization [45].

Energy and Environmental Sustainability

As much as spectral efficiency is enhanced by RL, it may be costly to compute, and this issue is a concern for carbon footprints and sustainability. To meet the green 6G objectives, it is necessary to develop energy-conscious and lightweight RL frameworks [77].

Legal and Regulatory Implications

Since RL-based power distribution is automated, the issue of accountability arises when failures to provide services or unjust distributions occur. There is a need for policymakers and regulators to establish accountability structures and compliance regulations on AI-based 6G systems [62].

Table 9: Summary of Case Studies and ELSI Considerations

Section	Focus Area	Key Insights	References (2020-2025)
Case Study 1	VEC with MIMO-NOMA	Decentralized DRL improved SE and latency under high mobility	[41]
Case Study 2	UAV-assisted NOMA	MARL enabled energy-efficient offloading and resilient connectivity	[52]
Case Study 3	VLC-NOMA with IRS	Two-agent DRL enhanced throughput and fairness in optical networks	[46]
Case Study 4	Federated Meta-RL	Enabled privacy-preserving, scalable PA across multi-cell NOMA	[71]
ELSI - Fairness	Bias in power allocation	Risks of marginalizing weaker users	[58]
ELSI - Transparency	Explainability	Need for interpretable RL in critical 6G applications	[87]
ELSI - Privacy	Data security	FRL protects user data but needs standardization	[45]
ELSI - Sustainability	Energy efficiency	Lightweight RL models required to reduce carbon footprint	[77]
ELSI - Legal	Regulation	Accountability frameworks for AI-driven allocation	[62]

5. Conclusions

This systematic review included the synthesis and critical analysis of the latest advancements in RL-based power allocation in NOMA-enabled 6G networks, with a particular focus on spectral efficiency, interference management, and co-existence with MEC. Out of 7,842 publications that were screened, 52 were included, which include various RL algorithms, i.e., Q-learning, DQN, actor-critic models, and DDPG, as well as multi-agent models. In these works, RL was shown to have the ability to improve spectral efficiency, energy efficiency, and scalability, besides adopting dynamically varying traffic conditions and user movements in a crowded network environment.

Despite these benefits, certain acute challenges remain unaddressed. The current methods often exhibit computational and energy complexities, face scaling constraints in ultra-dense systems, rely on ideal CSI, and neglect equitable resource distribution. Moreover, although a combination of RL and upcoming 6G technologies like IRS, UAVs, THz communications, and

federated MEC has potential, end-to-end joint optimization policies remain underutilised to date. Considering these results, it can be concluded that an RL-based power distribution is a capable and scalable paradigm to satisfy the strict performance demands of 6G and beyond-6G (B6G) systems. Nevertheless, to exploit its potential, this is going to need the development of scalable, computationally efficient, fairness-based, and explainable RL models. The focus of future research must in particular include: (i) decentralized and multi-agent RL systems and applications to large-scale deployments, (ii) lightweight and energy-conscious RL systems and applications to IoT and MEC devices, (iii) multi-objective RL systems and applications to support mission-critical 6G services, and (iv) transparent and interpretable RL.

These gaps will eventually speed up the achievement of intelligent, adaptive, and high-performance wireless communication systems that can be used to support the ambitious objectives of 6G and usher in the B6G era.

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Declarations

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Authors' Contributions

Ogenyi Fabian Chukwudi (OFC): Conceived the study, led the literature search and analysis, and drafted the manuscript. **Ugwu Chinyere Nneoma (UCN):** Contributed to methodology design and interpretation of findings. **Ugwu Okechukwu Paul-Chima (UOPC):** Supervised the research and contributed to review and editing. **Okon Michael Ben (OMB):** Assisted in drafting and data analysis. **Eze Val Hyginus Udoka (EVHU):** Contributed to conceptualization and supervision. **Ugwu Jovita Nnenna (UJN):** Participated in drafting and manuscript editing. **Enerst Edozie (EE):** Contributed to review and editing. **Ukagwu Kelechi John (UKJ):** Contributed to data synthesis and editing. **Mundu M. Mustafa (MMM):** Assisted in final review and supervision. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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List of Abbreviations

6G - Sixth Generation
5G - Fifth Generation
AI - Artificial Intelligence
AI - Age of Information
AWGN - Additive White Gaussian Noise
CSI - Channel State Information
DDPG - Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
DQN - Deep Q-Network
DRL – Deep Reinforcement Learning
EE - Energy Efficiency
EE-Aware – Energy-Efficiency Aware
ELSI - Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications
eMBB - Enhanced Mobile Broadband
FRL - Federated Reinforcement Learning
GNN - Graph Neural Network
HetNet - Heterogeneous Network

IoT - Internet of Things
IRS - Intelligent Reflecting Surface
MAMP-DQN - Multi-Agent Mean-Field Prioritized Deep Q-Network
MARL – Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
MEC - Mobile Edge Computing
MIMO - Multiple Input Multiple Output
mmWave - Millimeter Wave
mMTC - Massive Machine-Type Communications
NOMA - Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
OMA - Orthogonal Multiple Access
PA - Power Allocation
PER - Prioritized Experience Replay
QoS - Quality of Service
RA - Resource Allocation
RIS - Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RL - Reinforcement Learning
RQ - Research Question
SAC - Soft Actor-Critic
SE - Spectral Efficiency
SIC - Successive Interference Cancellation
SLR - Systematic Literature Review
TDMA - Time Division Multiple Access
THz - Terahertz
UAV - Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
URLLC - Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications
VEC - Vehicular Edge Computing
VLC - Visible Light Communication
XRL - Explainable Reinforcement Learning

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List of Figures

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection.

The PRISMA 2020-based diagram illustrates the flow of studies through the systematic review process. Out of 7,842 records initially identified, 312 duplicates were removed, leaving 7,530 records for screening. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 52 articles were included in the final review.

Figure 2: Distribution of Retrieved Articles across Databases.

Bar chart showing the number of retrieved studies per database (2010-2024). IEEE Xplore and Scopus contributed the highest number of articles, confirming their dominance in wireless communication research.

Figure 3: Number of Publications per Year (2010-2024)

Yearly publication trend for RL-based NOMA power allocation. The figure shows steady growth after 2016, with a peak between 2021-2023.

Figure 4: Publications per Outlet (Journal vs. Conference)

Distribution of included studies by type of outlet. Journals accounted for 71.2% (37 studies), while conferences contributed 28.8% (15 studies).

Figure 5: Distribution of Journal Publishers (2010-2024)

Bar chart showing the share of included publications by publisher. IEEE Xplore led with 20 (38.5%) publications, followed by Scopus (15), Web of Science (10), SpringerLink (5), and Wiley (2).

Figure 6: Research Issues versus Future Directions in AI-driven RL for 6G Networks. *Conceptual diagram mapping current unresolved issues (scalability, imperfect CSI, fairness, energy efficiency) to future research directions (multi-agent RL, transfer learning, energy-aware frameworks, explainability)*